

SYMPTOMS OF DEPRESSION AND ANXIETY IN KERATOCONUS PATIENT

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Abstract

Background: The slowly progressive corneal disorder keratoconus significantly impairs eyesight and quality of life, thereby increasing the likelihood of depression in those who have it. Using the Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS) at the AL-Ibrahim Eye Hospital in Karachi, the purpose of this study was to determine how frequently anxiety and depression occur in keratoconus patients.

Methods: A descriptive analytical study was conducted at the Al -Ibrahim eye hospital Karachi, in March to April 2021, and patients diagnosed with symptomatic keratoconus were recruited through a non-probability convenient sampling technique. After written informed consent from patients, the severity of keratoconus was assessed using Visual acuity and corneal topography. Symptoms of anxiety and depression were assessed through Hospital Anxiety and Depression (HADS) scale. Data was entered and analyzed by using SPSS V.20.0. Mean and \pm SD was computed for continuous variables like age and visual acuity. Frequency and percentage was calculated for qualitative variables like gender and severity of keratoconus. Spearman's correlation was used to check the correlation between the severity of Keratoconus and the HADS score.

Results: A total of 108 participants, of which 60 (56%) were female and 48 (44%) were male. By employing the Hospital Anxiety Depression scale (HADS), 44 (40.7%) patients were classified as normal with a HADS score of (0-7), 23 (21.3%) as borderline with a HADS score of (8-10) and 41 (38%) patients were diagnosed with anxiety and depression with a HADS score of (11-21).

Conclusion: Depression and anxiety are very common among keratoconus patients, especially in the advanced stages of the disease.

INTRODUCTION

Keratoconus is the most common progressive, non-inflammatory, bilateral eye disease that is characterized by corneal thinning. Because of the steepness of the cornea, it becomes cone-shaped and bulges out towards the center of the cornea in areas of greatest thinning, resulting in irregular

astigmatism and nearsightedness. Keratoconus is thought to affect 54 people out of every 100,000 in the general population (Romero-Jiménez et al., 2010). Depending on the region, the prevalence of keratoconus ranges from 0.3 per 100,000 in Russia to 2,300 per 100,000 in Central India (Althomali et

al., 2018). The early stages of keratoconus are asymptomatic but as the condition worsens, visual blurring, problems seeing at night, and sensitivity to strong light are among the symptoms. Patients with keratoconus could also have rapid changes in their eyeglass prescription (Nelson-Ayifah et al., 2017).

Keratoconus has been mostly characterized according to its keratometric readings, deformed mires, and cone size. Using various corneal topography maps, the stages of keratoconus are categorised according to corneal topographical findings, corneal curvature and shape changes (Munsamy & Moodley, 2017). Among the most prevalent diseases in both primary care and the general population are depression and anxiety disorders and both of these are interlinked. In 2018, Lim et al. reported that 90% study participants who had anxiety disorder also reported of depression symptoms, and about 85% of those who had depression, reported major anxiety (Lim et al., 2018). Depression is a frequent psychiatric condition that manifests as low self-worth, guilt, gloomy mood, lower energy, altered sleep or eating patterns, and mental confusion (Karadağ & Sölpük, 2018). Anxiety is a feeling of agitation and unease brought on by the thought of a potentially hazardous situation. In 1950, Rollo May described anxiety as the pressure to cope with loneliness or the perception of unpopularity or disapproval (Iyer & Khan, 2012).

According to WHO predictions, depression will overtake heart disease as the second most common cause of death worldwide in another ten years. Currently, one in five women and twelve men worldwide suffer from depression (Nelson-Ayifah et al., 2017). In those with eye disorders, depression or depressive symptoms were 25% more common and diabetic eye disease was associated with the highest rate of depression (29%), followed by glaucoma (25%), age-related macular degeneration (24%), and cataracts (23%) (Goldman et al., 1999). Keratoconus is also a visual debilitating disorder, generally manifesting in earlier adult life with rapid visual loss and resultant difficulties in personal and professional lives of patients. Therefore, it is essential to understand the association of this condition with the occurrence of depression and anxiety to better manage the quality of life in this disease.

Objective:

The objective of this study was to evaluate the occurrence of depression and anxiety symptoms in patients having keratoconus attending cornea clinic at AIEH, Karachi to suggest better treatment and identify the ways to overcome depression caused by keratoconus.

Methodology

This descriptive, analytical study was approved by the institutional research and ethical committee and adhered to the principles of the Helsinki declaration. Verbal explanations of the method were given to each participant in the study. Each one of them provided written, fully informed consent in both English and Urdu. The study design was conducted at AEIH, Karachi. The Open Epi sample calculator determined the sample size to be 108, and the prevalence of keratoconus was 8.04% (95% C.I. and 5% margin of error) (Snaith, 2003). The degree of keratoconus was determined by corneal topography findings using Topcon CA-800 Corneal Analyzer (Topcon, Tokyo, Japan). Using the Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS), symptoms of anxiety and depression were evaluated. The HADS consists of 14 questions, 7 of which are dedicated to anxiety and 7 to depression. The HADS scale has three categories: normal (0-7), borderline (8-10), and abnormal (11-21) case of anxiety and depression (Moschos et al., 2018).

Data was entered and analyzed by using SPSS V.20.0. Mean and \pm SD were computed for continuous variables like age. Frequency and percentage were calculated for qualitative variables like gender. Spearman's correlation was used to check the correlation between the severity of Keratoconus and the HADS score.

Results:

A total of 108 people participated in this study, of whom 60 (56%) were women and 48 (44%) were men. The patients' average age was 25.25 ± 6.39 years. Participants had an age range of 70 patients between the ages of 18 and 25, 28 patients between the ages of 26 and 35, and just 10 patients between the ages of 36 and 45 years. Out of 108 individuals, 41 (38.0%) had advanced keratoconus, 38 (35.2%) had moderate keratoconus, and 21 (19.4%) had

severe keratoconus. The remaining 8 (7.4%) patients had mild keratoconus (Table 1).

By employing the Hospital Anxiety Depression scale (HADS), 44 patients were classified as normal with a HADS score of (0-7), 23 as borderline with a HADS score of (8-10) and 41 patients were diagnosed with anxiety and depression with a HADS score of (11-21) (Table 2). By gender distribution, (20.4%) of both males and females were normal, while (10.2%) of males and (11.1%) of females were borderline, and (13.9%) of males and (24.1%) of females were abnormal HADS scores.

Table 3 showed the correlation between the Severity of Keratoconus and HADS Score. A total of 8 participants with mild keratoconus, 7 (87.5%)

reported having normal HADS scores, 1(12.5%) having borderline HADS scores, and none having abnormal HADS scores. Out of 38 subjects with moderate keratoconus, 27(71%) reported having a normal, and 8(21%) having a borderline, and just 3(8%) having an abnormal HADS score. In a total of 41 advanced keratoconus patients, 9(22%) were in the normal range, 11(27%) were on the borderline, and 21(51%) have an abnormal HADS score. Out of 21 patients with severe keratoconus, only 1(5%) individual with severe keratoconus have a normal HADS score, while 3(14%) have a borderline HADS score. However, 17(81%) have an abnormal; HADS score.

Severity of keratoconus	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Mild	8	7.4
Moderate	38	35.2
Advanced	41	38
Severe	21	19.4
Total	108	100

Table 1 Frequency distribution of severity in Keratoconus in study population

HADS Score	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Normal (0-7)	44	40.7
Borderline (8-10)	23	21.3
Abnormal (11-21)	41	38
Total	108	100

Table 2 Frequency distribution of severity of depression & anxiety as reported in HADS Score in study population

Severity of Keratoconus	HADS Score			Total	p-value
	Normal	Borderline abnormal	Abnormal		
Mild	7 87.5%	1 12.5%	0 0%	8 100%	0.001
Moderate	27 71%	8 21%	3 8%	38 100%	
Advanced	9 22%	11 27%	21 51%	41 100%	
Severe	1 5%	3 14%	17 81%	21 100%	
Total	44	23	41	108	

Table 3 Correlation between Severity of Keratoconus and HADS Score

Discussion:

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study in Pakistan to evaluate the prevalence of anxiety and depression in adult keratoconus patients and the relationship between the severity of keratoconus and the HADS score. In this study, 38% of patients were diagnosed with severe anxiety and depression, but in a study conducted by Marmara University's Faculty of Medicine's Department of Psychiatry, (12.5%) of patients were identified with severe depressive symptoms (Muacevic et al., 2021). The first cause for the differences in rates could be due to different sample sizes, the second to the different scale employed, and the participant's social and economic circumstances.

Findings from our study (38%) of participants suffered from anxiety and depression, which is closely consistent with the study carried out in Saudi Arabia in which depression was found to be present in (40.6%) of keratoconus patients (Naderan et al., 2016).

In our study, the levels of normal and moderate anxiety and depression did not significantly differ between men and women, but the levels of severe anxiety and depression were significantly higher in women than in men. This finding is supported by a study conducted in **Mekelle Quiha General Hospital Ophthalmic Clinic in North Ethiopia, which found** females were three times more likely to experience depression than males (Zheng et al., 2017). Another study conducted in Australia also supports that anxiety and depression are the major issues for adult females, compared with males. The associated factors for increased depression in female patients include residence in remote areas where people have less interaction with mental health services rather than in metropolitan areas probably due to lack of service availability or no access to the services (Naderan et al., 2016).

In our study, we demonstrated that keratoconus is the leading cause of depression and anxiety, compared to other eye disorders, the most common was diabetic eye disease (DED), which had a frequency of (29%), followed by glaucoma patients (25%), age-related macular degeneration (AMD) patients (24%), and cataract (23%).

When compared to the other four common chronic diseases in Pakistan, the frequency of depression in anemia, hypertension, diabetes, and asthma was

(90%), (47%), (26%), and (23%) respectively (Godil et al., 2017). Our results imply that not just visual impairment but also the disease itself plays a crucial role in the development of anxiety and depression as the keratoconus patients in our study did not experience other prevalent causes of depression. Detecting and treating anxiety and depression is simple, especially in the early stages. Patients who have vision problems are more likely to experience depression, especially as they age. Practitioners of eye care should be aware of this. Ophthalmologists and optometrists may use screening instruments like PHQ-9 and HAD to identify depressed and anxiety symptoms even in the early stages and encourage rapid referral for psychiatric evaluation and potential treatment. We recommend that practitioners add anxiety and depression assessments in order to identify and refer patients to focused mental health care due to the lack of models covering these topics in eye care practice. Better outreach strategies might also be required to draw patients, particularly those who are sad, and make it easier for them to participate in vision rehabilitation.

Conclusion:

Patients with keratoconus frequently experience depression and anxiety, especially when the condition is advanced. We strongly advise keratoconus patients in both primary care and ophthalmology clinics to undergo depression screening. Clinically, ophthalmologists and optometrists should offer psychological help and keep in mind early referral to psychiatrists which might also potentially enhance the patient's quality of life when treating keratoconus patients.

Statements and Declarations:

Ethical approval and consent to participate:

Ethical approval and consent to participate was received from all participants.

Consent for publication:

Personal data of individuals was obtained after filling consent form and no data was included for publication.

Availability of data and material:

Complete data and material is available and can be shared if required.

Competing Interest

All authors declare that they have no competing interest. The authors don't have any conflict of interest or financial disclosure

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Consent Form

تحریری اجازت نامہ

تحقیق میں حصہ لینے والے امیدوار کا اعلامیہ:

1. میں معلوماتی فارم کو پڑھ چکا/چکی ہوں۔
2. میں سمجھتا / سمجھتی ہوں جو مقاصد اور خطرات اس تحقیق کے پروجیکٹ میں بتائے گئے ہیں۔
3. میں اس بات کی اجازت دیتا / دیتی ہوں کہ جو میرے متعلق معلومات کی جائے گی وہ صرف اس تحقیق کی حد تک محدود ہوگی۔
4. میں اپنی رضامندی سے اس تحقیق میں حصہ لے رہا/رہی ہوں اور سمجھتا / سمجھتی ہوں کہ میں آزاد ہوں کسی بھی وقت اس تحقیق سے دستبردار ہونے کا/کی۔

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Keratoconus is a cornea-related disorder that leads to compromised vision and affects the quality of life.

This study examined how keratoconus patients responded to anxiety and depressive symptoms questionnaire.

This study investigated the relationship between anxiety and depression in advanced stages of keratoconus.

REFERENCES:

- Althomali, T. A., Al-Qurashi, I. M., Al-Thagafi, S. M., Mohammed, A., & Almalki, M. (2018). Prevalence of keratoconus among patients seeking laser vision correction in Taif area of Saudi Arabia. *Saudi J Ophthalmol*, 32(2), 114-118. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sjopt.2017.11.003>
- Godil, A., Mallick, M. S. A., Adam, A. M., Haq, A., Khetpal, A., Afzal, R., Salim, M., & Shahid, N. (2017). Prevalence and Severity of Depression in a Pakistani Population with at least One Major Chronic Disease. *J Clin Diagn Res*, 11(8), Oc05-oc10. <https://doi.org/10.7860/jcdr/2017/27519.10329>
- Goldman, L. S., Nielsen, N. H., & Champion, H. C. (1999). Awareness, diagnosis, and treatment of depression. *J Gen Intern Med*, 14(9), 569-580. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1525-1497.1999.03478.x>
- Iyer, K., & Khan, Z. (2012). Review paper depression—A review. *Research Journal of Recent Sciences* ___ ISSN, 2277, 2502.
- Karadağ, E., & Sölpük, N. (2018). Relationship between depression and anxiety symptoms in studies conducted in Turkey: A meta-analysis study.
- Lim, G. Y., Tam, W. W., Lu, Y., Ho, C. S., Zhang, M. W., & Ho, R. C. (2018). Prevalence of Depression in the Community from 30 Countries between 1994 and 2014. *Sci Rep*, 8(1), 2861. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-21243-x>
- Moschos, M. M., Gouliopoulos, N. S., Kalogeropoulos, C., Androudi, S., Kitsos, G., Ladas, D., Tsatsos, M., & Chatziralli, I. (2018). Psychological aspects and depression in patients with symptomatic keratoconus. *Journal of Ophthalmology*, 2018.
- Muacevic, A., Adler, J., Al-Dairi, W., Al Saeed, A., & Alsaad, A. (2021). Depression Among Keratoconus Patients in Saudi Arabia. *Cureus*, 12(12).
- Munsamy, A. J., & Moodley, V. R. (2017). A correlation analysis of cone characteristics and central keratometric readings for the different stages of keratoconus. *Indian J Ophthalmol*, 65(1), 7-11. https://doi.org/10.4103/ijo.IJO_980_15
- Naderan, M., Rajabi, M. T., Zarrinbakhsh, P., Naderan, M., & Bakhshi, A. (2016). Association between family history and keratoconus severity. *Current eye research*, 41(11), 1414-1418.
- Nelson-Ayifah, D., Kobia-acquah, E., Ahmed, A., & Ben, K. (2017). Profile of keratoconus in selected eye clinics, accra: a retrospective study. *Ophthalmology and Vision Science*, 1, 8-16.
- Romero-Jiménez, M., Santodomingo-Rubido, J., & Wolffsohn, J. S. (2010). Keratoconus: a review. *Cont Lens Anterior Eye*, 33(4), 157-166; quiz 205. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clae.2010.04.006>
- Snaith, R. P. (2003). The hospital anxiety and depression scale. *Health and quality of life outcomes*, 1(1), 1-4.
- Zheng, Y., Wu, X., Lin, X., & Lin, H. (2017). The prevalence of depression and depressive symptoms among eye disease patients: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Scientific reports*, 7(1), 1-9.